

Competitiveness Analysis of ASEAN Countries

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to identify the significant level of competitiveness among the ASEAN countries. We also pointed out that the distinction between the 6 original members and 4 new members of ASEAN does not exist on the basis of economic competitiveness. Secondary data obtained through the annual report of Global Competitiveness Index produced by the World Economic Forum was used. The scores of the 12 pillars for competitiveness were reanalyzed using discrete and continuous probability. We examined intra-group comparison and individual country analyses. The standard score and corresponding cumulative distribution were used for intra-group analysis. The Kahneman-Tversky Prospective Theory was used to analyze the country competitive prospect. We found that, as a group ASEAN countries are not competitive economies ($p > 0.05$). We obtained the linear predictive function for the expected value of competitiveness index score as $Y = 4.15 + 0.03X$. The F test shows 2.13 for the observed ($F(8,8) = 3.44$) with R squared of 0.23 implying that the competitiveness index for ASEAN is intrinsically diverse and is not stable; it could be improved.

Keywords: ASEAN, competitiveness, continuous probability, discrete probability, Global Competitiveness Index.

JEL Code: D72, F15, F55, E10, L16, O31, O40

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) consists of ten countries: Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. Traditionally, ASEAN analysis generally entails the breaking down of these ten countries into two groups: Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar and Vietnam are generally classified as “new members” which entails lowered economic status due to their lower GDP and underdeveloped physical infrastructure. The remaining six countries were considered founding members and are more economically developed. However, in this paper, we assert that this differentiation between old and new ASEAN members no longer exists in competitiveness analysis.

The purpose of this paper is to analyze competitiveness of the ASEAN countries based on multi-faceted components of competitiveness, called 12 pillars. These 12 pillars consist of: (i) institutions, (ii) infrastructure, (iii) ICT adoption, (iv) macroeconomic stability, (v) health, (vi) skills, (vii) product market, (viii) labor, (ix) financial system, (x) market size, (xi) business dynamism, and (xii) innovation capabilities (WEF’s annual report on Global Competitiveness Index, 2017-2018; see Appendix 1).

The intended contribution of this paper to debunk the differentiation of ASEAN countries into category as unsupportable when these countries are analyzed on the basis of competitiveness; these countries are uniformly uncompetitive with the exception of Singapore.

Table 1. ASEAN-10 countries with GDP (2014 – 2018)

Country	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Brunei	80,221	79,637	77,422	78,196	79,726
Cambodia	3,280	3,502	3,740	4,012	4,321
Indonesia	10,661	11,156	11,719	12,377	13,162
Laos	6,022	6,430	6,870	7,365	7,932
Malaysia	25,088	26,228	27,292	29,040	30,857
Myanmar	5,074	5,442	5,790	6,243	6,802
Philippines	6,953	7,331	7,810	8,314	8,893
Singapore	85,227	87,043	89,103	93,905	98,014
Thailand	15,596	16,198	16,909	17,855	18,943
Vietnam	5,657	6,035	6,423	6,913	7,462

Per capita GDP in US dollar. Source: IMF’s annual report of World Economic Outlook, 2018.

The classification of the ASEAN countries into two groups based on per capita GDP appears to be justifiable. However, this standard of classification focuses on the economic output, not the process that contributes to that output. As the result, it is difficult to assess the country’s prospect for sustainability. In this paper, we propose that competitiveness may be used as an indicator for the country’s prospect or growth and sustainability. We assert that under competitiveness analysis, the tradition classification of ASEAN countries into two groups disappeared. All countries, except Singapore, failed in competitiveness test under 80/20 threshold.

Table 2. Contradicting evidence against categorizing ASEAN into two groups

Country	2018*	Mean	S	Z	F(Z)	Status
Brunei	79,726	27,611.20	33,476.44	1.56	0.9410	Pass
Cambodia	4,321	27,611.20	33,476.44	-0.70	0.2433	Fail
Indonesia	13,162	27,611.20	33,476.44	-0.43	0.3331	Fail
Laos	7,932	27,611.20	33,476.44	-0.59	0.2784	Fail
Malaysia	30,857	27,611.20	33,476.44	0.10	0.5386	Fail
Myanmar	6,802	27,611.20	33,476.44	-0.62	0.2671	Fail
Philippines	8,893	27,611.20	33,476.44	-0.56	0.2881	Fail
Singapore	98,014	27,611.20	33,476.44	2.10	0.9833	Pass

Thailand	18,943	27,611.20	33,476.44	-0.26	0.3979	Fail
Vietnam	7,462	27,611.20	33,476.44	-0.60	0.2737	Fail

*Using FY2018 per capita GDP as latest figure to determined cumulative probability.

Only two countries (Brunei and Singapore) justified the categorization of the ASEAN into two groups of developed and undeveloped economies. Under the DeMoivre-Laplace Theorem, the probability of support the categorization is $F(Z) = 0.4878$ or 48.78% which is below our specified threshold of 80%.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Competitiveness of nations and intra-regional competitiveness

Competitiveness had been defined variously in the literature. For instance, at the firm level, it means meeting customer needs more readily than other firms (Edmonds 2000: 20). Competitiveness is overcoming commercial rivals (Law 2009). The key to success in firm level competition is price (Black *et al.* 2009). Some authors also analyzed this topic in the context of competitiveness of nations. The OECD, for instance see competitiveness in a broader context: “The ability of companies, industries, regions, nations or supranational regions to generate, while being and remaining exposed to international competition, relatively high factor income and factor employment levels on a sustainable basis” (Hatzichronoglou 1996: 20). The World Economic Forum (WEF) defines competitiveness as: “The set of institutions, policies, and factors that determine the level of productivity of a country. The level of productivity, in turn, sets the sustainable level of prosperity that can be earned by an economy” (Schwab 2009: 4). This paper uses the WEF’s standard and data for competitiveness measurement.

In the International Institute for Management Development’s (IMD) World Competitiveness Yearbook: a condensed definition and an academic definition (Garelli 2005): “Competitiveness of Nations is a field of economic theory, which analyses the fact and policies that shape the ability of a nation to create and maintain an environment that sustains more value creation for its enterprises and more prosperity for its people”. Inter-regional competitive analysis had been researched (Snieška and Bruneckienė, 2009: 46). However, intra-regional competitiveness is still not explored in detailed. This paper intended to contribute to the intra-regional competitiveness analysis literature.

2.2 Determining factors and measurement of competitiveness

Some writers assert that innovation is keyed to competitiveness (Ciocanel and Pavelescu, 2015). In the study of competitiveness, most papers focused on industry and firm level (Zelga, 2017). However, our paper looks at the competitiveness level at a country and regional contexts.

There is no single method for measuring competitiveness. It has been urged that “There is a big range of competitiveness measurement techniques, the most prominent and appealing of which are the Global Competitiveness Report of the WEF, the World Competitiveness Yearbook of IMD, and the Business Competitiveness of IFC-Ease of Doing Business Report” (Arslan and Tathdil, 2012).

It has been suggested that the concept of competitiveness is complex. Therefore, effective measure of competitiveness must use composite of indicator (Siudek and Zawojcka, 2014). The OECD's approach to measuring competitiveness also employs “composite indicator for outcome competitiveness consisting of income, social and ecological pillars...” This paper examined the competitiveness composite developed by the WEF called 12 pillars. These 12 pillars consists of: (i) institutions, (ii) infrastructure, (iii) ICT adoption, (iv) macroeconomic stability, (v) health, (vi) skills, (vii) product market, (ix) financial system, (x) market size, (xi) business dynamism, and (xii) innovation capabilities (The Global Competitiveness Report 2017–2018).

It is not the intent of this paper to propose a method for measuring competitiveness, but to analyze the result of competitiveness index reported by the WEF. We intend to accomplish this task by testing competitiveness index of ASEAN countries under continuous and discrete probabilities.

3.0 DATA AND METHODOLOGY

This paper is based on secondary data. The data comes from the Annual Global Competitiveness Report by World Economic Forum (WEF). We used this secondary data as the basis for the statistical calculation to verify intra-group significance levels for various competitiveness pillars.

There are two layers of analysis presented in this paper. On the one hand, we did intra-group analysis where each country is compared to the group performance of global competitive index. The intra-group analysis allowed us to see each country's performance in relations to its ASEAN cohorts. On the other, we analyzed the components of the 12 pillars on a country-basis. Country level analysis allowed us to see the strength and weakness of each country.

3.1 Intra-group analysis

In the first layer of analysis, we looked as ASEAN as a group. The competitiveness measurement for the ASEAN was used as a reference value against which each country was gauged for significant level of competitiveness. This verification was accomplished by using the standard score:

$$Z = \frac{X_{country} - X_{group}}{S_{group}} \tag{1}$$

With known standard score (Z), the percentage probability is determined:

$$F(Z) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\left(-\sqrt{\pi}\left(\beta_1 Z^5 + \beta_2 Z^3 + \beta_3 Z\right)\right)} \tag{2}$$

where $\beta_1 = 0.0004406$; $\beta_2 = 0.0318198$; and $\beta_3 = 0.900000$. In the group analysis, it is assumed that the values of competitiveness index are continuous distributed normally as:

$$f(x_i, \dots, x_n | \mu, \sigma^2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \tag{3}$$

The likelihood of the CDF is given by $f(x_i, \dots, x_n | \mu, \sigma^2) = \prod_{i=1}^n f(x_i | \mu, \sigma^2)$ or written as:

$$f(x_i, \dots, x_n | \mu, \sigma^2) = \left(\frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2}\right)^{n/2} \exp\left(-\frac{\sum (x_i - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \tag{4}$$

Alternatively:

$$f(x_i, \dots, x_n | \mu, \sigma^2) = \left(\frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2}\right)^{n/2} \exp\left(-\frac{\sum (x_i - \mu)^2 + n(\bar{x} - \mu)^2}{\sigma^2}\right) \tag{5}$$

For frequency analysis of success for the ASEAN region, the DeMoivre-Laplace Theorem (Walker, 1985) was used:

$$Z = \frac{X_{\geq 0.80} - np}{\sqrt{npq}} \tag{6}$$

where $X_{\geq 0.80}$ = number of composite of competitiveness passing 80% threshold; $n = 12$ pillars of WEF's competitiveness index; and $p = (s + 1)/(n + 2)$.

3.2 Country-by-country analysis of competitiveness

In the second layer of analysis, we looked at each country's competitiveness and to assess each country for competitiveness. According to WEF's global competitiveness index, there are 12 pillars. Each pillar is comprised of its relevant components (Index 1).

The WEF's competitiveness scoring system is based on 1-7 scale. The number of components for each pillar differs. For our analysis, we weighted the pillar with equal weight as: $W = w_1 + w_2 + \dots + w_n$ where $n = 12$ and $w_i = w_i/n$; thus, each pillar becomes: $P_i = w_i p_i$. Following the Kahneman-Tversky Prospect Theory function (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979):

$$V = \sum_{i=1}^n \pi(p_i)v(x_i) \tag{7}$$

where V = over-all expected utility, π = probability of each outcome p_i ; v = function for the assigned value to the outcome; and x_i = individual decision. In this paper, we modified the probability for each outcome to be a weighted probability; thus:

$$\hat{V} = \sum_{i=1}^n \pi(wp_i)v(x_i) \tag{8}$$

The probability of change at any given value, based on the observation of other pillar components, is determined by the discrete probability equation"

$$P(x) = \frac{n!}{(n-x)!x!} p^x(1-p)^{n-x} \tag{9}$$

where $p = (s + 1)/(n + 2)$, n = number of observation, and x = given number of frequency whose probability is to be determined. Although the WEF's original report provides ranking of competitiveness of each country, this paper re-rank the countries in ASEAN and provide a means to estimate the prospect of new rank under binomial distribution (13).

The normal approximation of the discrete distribution for the number of counts in succeeding to be competitive according to the WEF's multi-composite may be given by:

$$\mu \pm 3\sigma = np \pm 3\sqrt{npq} \in (0, n) \text{ where } \mu = np \text{ with the condition that } n > 9\left(\frac{1-p}{p}\right) \text{ and}$$

$$n > 9\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) \text{ knowing that } p = (s + 1)/(n + 2) \text{ according to LaPlace's Rule of Success.}$$

4.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Recall that the 10 countries in ASEAN are normally classified into two groups: new (Cambodia, Myanmar, Laos and Vietnam) and old members (Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand). This dichotomy is couched under the idea of time in joining the organization; however, in reality, the classification is based on the level of economic development. Our findings from comparative competitive studies of these countries show that there is no significant different among them. If there should be empirical evidence of the ASEAN countries, it is that these countries are significantly similar in their lack of competitiveness, with the exception of Singapore which exceeds all expected values among the 12 pillars of competitiveness index. Using the Weibull QQ plot (appendix 3) to obtain the regression line for purposes of forecasting the expected value, the prospect for competitiveness index for each country is in Table 3.

Table 3. Observed and expected competitive index score for ASEAN countries

Country	$\bar{X}_{12\text{ pillars}}$	$Y_w = a + bX$	$y\hat{H}$	Residual
Brunei	61.43	$Y_w = 4.15 + 0.03X$	67.91	6.48
Cambodia	50.19		66.44	16.25
Indonesia	64.93		68.36	3.43
Laos	59.80		67.69	7.89
Malaysia	63.85		68.22	4.37
Philippines	62.13		68.00	5.87
Singapore	83.48		70.77	-12.70
Thailand	58.04		67.47	9.42
Vietnam	67.54		68.70	1.16

We tested for the stability of the competitiveness index score changes by using the F-test for to verify if there is significant difference between the observed and expected. The expected F score for (8,8) degrees of freedom is 3.44; the calculated F score is 2.13 with R-squared of 0.23 (Appendix 3). There is no significant difference between the observed and expected values of competitiveness index score of the 12 pillars for the 9 countries. It implies that the competitiveness index for the ASEAN countries is stable. The general finding shows that ASEAN fails competitiveness index significance test for 80% threshold, if the F test shows strong stability, it implies that the ASEAN countries will remain not competitive for some time to come.

4.1 ASEAN intra-group competitiveness

At the first level of analysis, we examined the 10 countries as a group. We employed Pareto standard where the threshold for defining competitiveness standard is 80%. In order to be considered “competitive”, the country must score at least 0.80 for each element of the Global Competitiveness Index score under the standard score equation. The results of cumulative density function (CDF) probability of 12 components of the Global Competitiveness Index are presented in tables 4 and 5.

Table 4. ASEAN intra-group competitiveness for 2018; $n = 9$

Country*	Inst.	Infra.	ICT	Macro	Health	Skills
Brunei	0.7370	0.7750	0.9350	0.4388	0.8897	0.8332
Cambodia	0.2428	0.2232	0.2776	0.4642	0.2979	0.1052
Indonesia	0.7262	0.6579	0.6957	0.9058	0.5558	0.7875
Laos	0.3134	0.3773	0.2413	0.2642	0.2170	0.3099
Malaysia	0.9310	0.8977	0.8511	0.9890	0.8345	0.9557
Philippines	0.4295	0.4343	0.5384	0.9104	0.4316	0.7553

Singapore	0.9938	0.9966	0.9833	0.9435	0.9902	0.9690
Thailand	0.4680	0.6174	0.2538	0.4861	0.8022	0.4718
Vietnam	0.6458	0.7361	0.5851	0.9089	0.9087	0.7581
<i>S**</i>	2	2	3	5	5	3
<i>P</i>	0.27	0.27	0.36	0.55	0.55	0.36
<i>Q</i>	0.73	0.73	0.64	0.45	0.45	0.64
<i>Z</i>	-0.34	-0.34	-0.19	1.49	1.49	-0.19
<i>F(Z)***</i>	0.3664	0.3664	0.4251	0.5242	0.5242	0.4251
<i>pValue</i>	0.6336	0.6336	0.5749	0.4758	0.4758	0.5749
<i>Conclude</i>	No sig.					

*Myanmar: data not available. **S = success, defined 0.80 as success. ***F(Z) = pValue significant at 0.05.

Among the first group of six components: (i) institutions, (ii) infrastructure, (iii) ICT adoption, (iv) macroeconomic stability, (v) health, and (vi) skills, sing 80% threshold for competitiveness, the number of countries that passed as: (i) institutions [2 countries], (ii) infrastructure [2 countries], (iii) ICT adoption [3 countries], (iv) macroeconomic stability [5 countries], (v) health [5 countries], (vi) skills [3 countries].

Table 5. ASEAN intra-group competitiveness for 2018

Country*	Prod Mk	Labor	Finance	Mk size	Bus Dyn	Innovation
Brunei	0.7985	0.8158	0.2610	0.1185	0.6031	0.4105
Cambodia	0.3749	0.6293	0.3157	0.2656	0.2172	0.3420
Indonesia	0.7196	0.5358	0.5825	0.9347	0.8628	0.4952
Laos	0.5207	0.4154	0.9412	0.8386	0.9300	0.8891
Malaysia	0.8694	0.9522	0.2632	0.1751	0.1161	0.2542
Philippines	0.6598	0.8258	0.6828	0.7937	0.7992	0.4979
Singapore	0.9990	0.9987	0.9727	0.8089	0.9392	0.9950
Thailand	0.4616	0.4253	0.5404	0.8055	0.4532	0.3976
Vietnam	0.5165	0.7839	0.9420	0.8651	0.8947	0.6265
<i>S**</i>	2	4	3	5	4	2
<i>P</i>	0.27	0.45	0.36	0.55	0.45	0.27
<i>Q</i>	0.73	0.55	0.64	0.45	0.55	0.73
<i>Z</i>	-0.34	-0.06	-0.19	1.49	-0.06	-0.34
<i>F(Z)***</i>	0.3664	0.4758	0.4251	0.5242	0.4758	0.3664
<i>pValue</i>	0.6336	0.5243	0.5749	0.4758	0.5243	0.6336
<i>Conclude</i>	No sig.					

*Myanmar: data not available. **S = success, defined 0.80 as success. ***F(Z) = pValue significant at 0.05.

Among the second group of six components: (vii) product market, (viii) labor, (ix) financial system, (x) market size, (xi) business dynamism, and (xii) innovation capabilities. Using 80% threshold for competitiveness, the number of countries that passed as: (vii) product market [2 countries], (viii) Labor [4 countries], (ix) financial system [3 countries], (x) market size [5 countries], (xi) business dynamism [4 countries], and (xii) innovation capabilities [2 countries].

As a region, ASEAN has a total standard score for success of being competitive of 0.007 or $F(Z) = 0.5028$ or approximately 50.28%. This result is obtained through success counts and employing the DeMoivre-Laplace Theorem:

$Z = (X_{\geq 0.80} - np) / \sqrt{npq}$. In order to reach 80% threshold, the Z score must be 0.84. The required success count is 92 among the 12 components of the Global Competitiveness Index ($s = 9$ countries

x 12 components = 108). Using the binomial distribution equation, we can determine the probability for achieving this threshold if $x = 92$; $P(92) \cong 0.000000000$. We conclude that as a region, ASEAN is not competitive based on 80% threshold as the standard for decision rule using the 12 composite of the WEF's Global Competitiveness Index.

4.2. ASEAN member countries competitiveness

In the second level of analysis, we examined individual countries to determine its current level of competitiveness. We used the CDF of each country's Global Competitive Index score as the unit of analysis. The result is presented in Table 6.

Table 6. ASEAN individual country competitiveness under WEF's 12 composites

Factors	1	2	3	4	5	6*	7	8	9	10
Institution	58.30	41.90	57.90	44.50	68.70	-	48.30	80.70	49.50	55.10
Infra.	71.30	51.70	66.80	57.50	77.90		59.40	95.70	65.40	69.70
ICT	76.20	44.40	61.10	42.70	69.10		54.80	85.20	43.30	56.60
Macro	73.70	74.40	89.70	68.50	100		90.00	92.60	75.00	89.90
Health	85.90	62.90	71.70	59.60	82.60		67.60	100	81.00	87.30
Skills	66.00	41.00	64.10	49.50	74.20		62.90	76.00	54.30	63.00
Product	60.90	50.00	58.50	53.50	63.60		56.90	81.20	52.10	53.40
Labor	64.20	59.70	57.80	55.40	70.20		64.50	80.20	55.60	63.30
Financial	51.20	53.60	63.90	84.10	51.30		67.90	89.30	62.30	84.20
Market	37.00	46.20	81.60	73.00	41.10		70.20	71.10	70.90	74.90
Bus. dyn.	58.50	45.30	69.00	73.80	40.10		65.80	74.70	53.70	71.00
Innovation	33.90	31.20	37.10	55.50	27.40		37.20	75.00	33.40	42.10
μ	57.18	57.18	57.18	57.18	57.18		57.18	57.18	57.18	57.18
σ	13.24	13.24	13.24	13.24	13.24		13.24	13.24	13.24	13.24
Z	-0.34	-1.04	-0.02	-0.27	-0.42		-0.17	1.60	-0.51	-0.51
$F(Z)$	0.37	0.15	0.49	0.39	0.34		0.43	0.95	0.31	0.31
p Value	0.63	0.85	0.51	0.61	0.66		0.57	0.05	0.69	0.69
Conclude	No sig		No sig	Sig.	No sig	No sig				

*6 (Myanmar) has missing data. Columns 1 – 10 are 10 countries of ASEAN.

The expected competitive level in probability term is $\mu = 0.31 \pm 0.25$. Only one country exceeds the 80% threshold: *Singapore*. The probability that other remaining 8 ASEAN countries (Myanmar not included due to missing data) will meet the 80% threshold is:

$$P(x) = \frac{n!}{(n-x)!x!} p^x (1-p)^{n-x} = 0.000258 \text{ or } 0.0258\% \text{ where } p = 0.31; q = 0.69, n = 12 \text{ factors, and } X = 10 \text{ for } 80\%.$$

Using the Khaneman-Tversky Prospect Theory, the result is consistent with our prior analysis. Only Singapore is able to placed itself at the center of the probability dispersion space with the referenced region of $F(Z) = 0.50$. Under this analytical approach, the further the country score falls from the center (0.50) the less the prospect that country has for being competitive under the 12 composites used by the WEF's Global Competitiveness Index.

Under the DeMoivre-Laplace Theorem, individual country analysis is summarized in Table 7. Only Singapore meets the standard of being competitive under 80% threshold.

Table 7. Country competitiveness prospect under DeMoivre-Laplace Theorem

Country*	X	n	P	Q	Z	$F(Z)$	Status
Brunei	4	12	0.36	0.64	-0.17	0.4317	Fail
Cambodia	0	12	0.07	0.93	-0.96	0.1682	Fail

Indonesia	3	12	0.29	0.71	-0.27	0.3922	Fail
Laos	3	12	0.29	0.71	-0.27	0.3922	Fail
Malaysia	8	12	0.64	0.36	0.17	0.5683	Fail
Philippines	2	12	0.21	0.79	-0.40	0.3439	Fail
Singapore	12	12	0.93	0.07	0.96	0.8318	Pass
Thailand	2	12	0.21	0.79	-0.40	0.3439	Fail
Vietnam	5	12	0.43	0.57	-0.08	0.4668	Fail

*Myanmar: data not available. **S = success, defined 0.80 as success. ***F(Z) = pValue significant at 0.05.

In order to qualified as competitive, among the 12 pillars the country must score at least 10 pillars whose CDF exceeds 80%. In this case, only Singapore meets the standard. This, we see that the classification of ASEAN countries into more developed and less developed is unsupported. It may be justified if the classification is based on per capita GDP (*see* Table 1). However, for economic analysis, the ASEAN economies, with the exception of Singapore, fail competitiveness test. Using F(Z) value in Table 4, under the likelihood function of Pareto distribution, the expected value for F(Z) is 0.42 where the threshold is 0.80.

We now turn to the Prospect Theory to verify how far away does the each country fall from being competitive. By using the CDF probability space of the Global Competitive Index, we center the utility score under the Kahneman-Tversky around the 0.50 center of the probability space. Any country that falls within the center ± 0.05 error is considered competitive; outside of this range is considered failure. We present the result in Table 8 and noted again that only Singapore is at the center of the probability space.

Table 8. ASEAN Competitive Index analysis under the Prospect Theory

Country	F(Z)	Weight	π	X	\hat{V}	\hat{V}_{50}
Brunei	0.37	0.09	0.37	52.68	1.78	0.05*
Cambodia	0.15	0.04	0.15	43.41	0.24	0.01
Indonesia	0.49	0.12	0.49	56.98	3.47	0.10
Laos	0.39	0.10	0.39	53.64	2.09	0.06
Malaysia	0.34	0.08	0.34	51.59	1.47	0.04
Philippines	0.43	0.11	0.43	54.87	2.58	0.07
Singapore	0.95	0.24	0.95	78.36	17.62	0.50
Thailand	0.31	0.08	0.31	50.45	1.18	0.03
Vietnam	0.56	0.14	0.56	59.04	4.58	0.13

*The centered prospect value is obtained by dividing the individual country prospect by the sum of 9 countries. Myanmar is not included in the group due to missing data.

5.0 CONCLUSION

This paper answer one simple research question: Are ASEAN economies competitive? The answer is “no.” ASEAN is not competitive as an economic community; individual countries in ASEAN are not competitive, except Singapore that passed the 80% threshold. We obtained the linear predictive function for the expected value of competitiveness index score as $Y = 4.15 + 0.03X$. The F test shows 2.13 for the observed ($F(8,8) = 3.44$) with R squared of 0.23 implying that the competitiveness index for ASEAN is intrinsically diverse and is not stable; it could be improved. Competitiveness may serve as a new indicator for country economic studies. In this paper, we use the Global Competitiveness Index produced by the WEF for the year of 2018 as the basis our study. The ten countries of the ASEAN are used as proxy. Despite differences in per capita GDP levels among the countries, when evaluated the countries on the basis of competitiveness, all countries failed ($p > 0.05$) except Singapore. If competitiveness leads to economic growth then

competitiveness index should be used to verify whether the economy has good prospect. Our finding also supports the urging of abandoning the categorizing ASEAN into two groups according to level of economic development. Our finding of cumulative probability to supporting such bifurcation is only 0.4878 ($p = 0.5122$).

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Appendix 1

Global Competitive Index Components

Source: World Economic Forum Global Competitive Index

<https://www.weforum.org/reports/the-global-competitiveness-report-2018>

Pillar 1: Institutions 0-100 (best)

- 1.01 Organized crime 1-7 (best)
- 1.02 Homicide rate /100,000 pop.
- 1.03 Terrorism incidence 0 (very high) -100 (no incidence)
- 1.04 Reliability of police services 1-7 (best)
- 1.05 Social capital 0-100 (high)
- 1.06 Budget transparency 0-100 (best)
- 1.07 Judicial independence 1-7 (best)
- 1.08 Efficiency of legal framework in challenging regulations 1-7 (best)
- 1.09 Freedom of the press 0-100 (worst)
- 1.10 Burden of government regulation 1-7 (best)
- 1.11 Efficiency of legal framework in settling disputes 1-7 (best)
- 1.12 E-Participation Index 0-1 (best)
- 1.13 Future orientation of government 1-7 (best)
- 1.14 Incidence of corruption 0-100 (best)
- 1.15 Property rights 1-7 (best)
- 1.16 Intellectual property protection 1-7 (best)
- 1.17 Quality of land administration 0-30 (best)
- 1.18 Strength of auditing and reporting standards 1-7 (best)
- 1.19 Conflict of interest regulation 0-10 (best)
- 1.20 Shareholder governance 0-10 (best)

Pillar 2: Infrastructure 0-100 (best)

- 2.01 Road connectivity index 0-100 (best)
- 2.02 Quality of roads 1-7 (best)
- 2.03 Railroad density km of roads/square km
- 2.04 Efficiency of train services 1-7 (best)
- 2.05 Airport connectivity score
- 2.06 Efficiency of air transport services 1-7 (best)
- 2.07 Liner Shipping Connectivity Index 0–157.1 (best)
- 2.08 Efficiency of seaport services 1-7 (best)
- 2.09 Electrification rate % pop.
- 2.10 Electric power transmission and distribution losses % output
- 2.11 Exposure to unsafe drinking water % pop.
- 2.12 Reliability of water supply 1-7 (best)

Pillar 3: ICT adoption 0-100 (best)

- 3.01 Mobile-cellular telephone subscriptions /100 pop.
- 3.02 Mobile-broadband subscriptions /100 pop.
- 3.03 Fixed-broadband Internet subscriptions /100 pop.
- 3.04 Fibre Internet subscriptions /100 pop.
- 3.05 Internet users % pop.

Pillar 4: Macroeconomic stability 0-100 (best)

- 4.01 Inflation annual % change
- 4.02 Debt dynamics 0-100 (best)

Pillar 5: Health 0-100 (best)

5.01 Healthy life expectancy years

Pillar 6: Skills 0-100 (best)

6.01 Mean years of schooling Years
6.02 Extent of staff training 1-7 (best)
6.03 Quality of vocational training 1-7 (best)
6.04 Skillset of graduates 1-7 (best)
6.05 Digital skills among population 1-7 (best)
6.06 Ease of finding skilled employees 1-7 (best)
6.07 School life expectancy Years
6.08 Critical thinking in teaching 1-7 (best)
6.09 Pupil-to-teacher ratio in primary education Ratio
Brunei Darussalam
Index Component

Pillar 7: Product market 0-100 (best)

7.01 Distortive effect of taxes and subsidies on competition 1-7 (best)
7.02 Extent of market dominance 1-7 (best)
7.03 Competition in services 1-7 (best)
7.04 Prevalence of non-tariff barriers 1-7 (best)
7.05 Trade tariffs % duty
7.06 Complexity of tariffs 1-7 (best)
7.07 Efficiency of the clearance process 1–5 (best)
7.08 Services trade openness 0-100 (worst)

Pillar 8: Labour market 0-100 (best)

8.01 Redundancy costs weeks of salary
8.02 Hiring and firing practices 1-7 (best)
8.03 Cooperation in Labour-employer relations 1-7 (best)
8.04 Flexibility of wage determination 1-7 (best)
8.05 Active Labour policies 1-7 (best)
8.06 Workers' rights 0-100 (best)
8.07 Ease of hiring foreign labour 1-7 (best)
8.08 Internal Labour mobility 1-7 (best)
8.09 Reliance on professional management 1-7 (best)
8.10 Pay and productivity 1-7 (best)
8.11 Female participation in Labour force ratio
8.12 Labour tax rate %

Pillar 9: Financial system 0-100 (best)

9.01 Domestic credit to private sector % GDP
9.02 Financing of SMEs 1-7 (best)
9.03 Venture capital availability 1-7 (best)
9.04 Market capitalization % GDP
9.05 Insurance premium % GDP
9.06 Soundness of banks 1-7 (best)
9.07 Non-performing loans % loan portfolio value
9.08 Credit gap percentage points
9.09 Banks' regulatory capital ratio ratio

Pillar 10: Market size 0-100 (best)

- 10.01 Gross domestic product PPP \$ billions
- 10.02 Imports % GDP

Pillar 11: Business dynamism 0-100 (best)

- 11.01 Cost of starting a business % GNI per capita
- 11.02 Time to start a business days
- 11.03 Insolvency recovery rate cents/\$
- 11.04 Insolvency regulatory framework 0-16 (best)
- 11.05 Attitudes toward entrepreneurial risk 1-7 (best)
- 11.06 Willingness to delegate authority 1-7 (best)
- 11.07 Growth of innovative companies 1-7 (best)
- 11.08 Companies embracing disruptive ideas 1-7 (best)

Pillar 12: Innovation capability 0-100 (best)

- 12.01 Diversity of workforce 1-7 (best)
- 12.02 State of cluster development 1-7 (best)
- 12.03 International co-inventions applications/million pop.
- 12.04 Multi-stakeholder collaboration 1-7 (best)
- 12.05 Scientific publications H Index
- 12.06 Patent applications applications/million pop.
- 12.07 R&D expenditures % GDP
- 12.08 Quality of research institutions index
- 12.09 Buyer sophistication 1-7 (best)
- 12.10 Trademark applications applications/million pop.

Appendix 2

WEF's Global Competitiveness Index Raw Score

Source: World Economic Forum Global Competitive Index

<https://www.weforum.org/reports/the-global-competitiveness-report-2018>

Appendix 2A: Global Competitiveness Index raw score

Country	Inst.	Infra.	ICT	Macro	Health	Skills
Brunei	58.30	71.30	76.20	73.70	85.90	66.00
Cambodia	41.90	51.70	44.40	74.40	62.90	41.00
Indonesia	57.90	66.80	61.10	89.70	71.70	64.10
Laos	44.50	57.50	42.70	68.50	59.60	49.50
Malaysia	68.70	77.90	69.10	100	82.60	74.20
Philippines	48.30	59.40	54.80	90.00	67.60	62.90
Singapore	80.70	95.70	85.20	92.60	100	76.00
Thailand	49.50	65.40	43.30	75.00	81.00	54.30
Vietnam	55.10	69.70	56.60	89.90	87.30	63.00

Appendix 2B: Global Competitiveness Index raw score

Country	Prod Mk	Labor	Finance	Mk size	Bus Dyn	Innovation
Brunei	60.90	64.20	51.20	37.00	58.50	33.90
Cambodia	50.00	59.70	53.60	46.20	45.30	31.20
Indonesia	58.50	57.80	63.90	81.60	69.00	37.10
Laos	53.50	55.40	84.10	73.00	73.80	55.50
Malaysia	63.60	70.20	51.30	41.10	40.10	27.40
Philippines	56.90	64.50	67.90	70.20	65.80	37.20
Singapore	81.20	80.20	89.30	71.10	74.70	75.00
Thailand	52.10	55.60	62.30	70.90	53.70	33.40
Vietnam	53.40	63.30	84.20	74.90	71.00	42.10

Appendix 3

Using Weibull QQ plot to obtain expected value of competitiveness index score

The predictive linear function of $Y = a + bX$ was obtained through Weibull QQ in the following steps.

Step 1. Calculate the time function $F(t)$

$$F(t) = \frac{(i - 0.3)}{(n + 0.4)}$$

where i = item number; and n = number of observation.

Step 2. Calculate the X and Y on the QQ plot

$$X = \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{1 - F(t)}\right)\right)$$

$$Y = \ln(X_i)$$

Step 3. Calculate intercept and slope of the linear line

$$I = \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y$$

$$II = \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2$$

where the slope is $b = \frac{I}{II}$ and intercept is $a = \bar{Y} - b\bar{X}$

Country	Y_i	\hat{Y}	$(Y_i - \hat{Y})^2$	$(\hat{Y} - \bar{Y})^2$	$(Y_i - \bar{Y})^2$
Brunei	61.43	67.91	41.99	19.56	4.23
Cambodia	50.19	66.44	264.06	8.72	176.83
Indonesia	64.93	68.36	11.76	23.74	2.08
Laos	59.80	67.69	62.25	17.66	13.60
Malaysia	63.85	68.22	19.10	22.39	0.13
Philippines	62.13	68.00	34.46	20.36	1.84
Singapore	83.48	70.77	161.54	53.03	399.69
Thailand	58.04	67.47	88.92	15.86	29.68
Vietnam	67.54	68.70	1.35	27.17	16.42
SSE			685.44		
SSR			208.48		
SST			893.92		
MSE = SSE/n-p-1			97.92		
MSR = SSR/p			208.48		
F = MSR / MSE			2.13		
R squared = SSR/SST*			0.23		

*SST = SSE + SSR